

Session 4 live-captioning, Wednesday, 21 June 2023:

[Galaxy surveys at high redshift](#)

Cosmin Ilie: Using Roman Space Telescope to find Dark Star candidates

And now, we will be in session 4. Okay. Let's welcome Cosmin. Discussion on using Roman to find dark star candidates. I would like to start by thanking the organizers for giving me the opportunity. A subject that has been fascinating me for a while. You might see here -- the main -- some of which dark matter. Dark stars. This slide. Dark stars -- first of all, they could shine as bright as the galaxy. Second of all, they are not made of dark matter. Yes, Michael? -- [indistinct] I'm not going to repeat what I just said. Can you hear me okay? Good? They are not made of dark matter. There may be part of them about 1% or less. They are not dark about they are not made of dark matter. Now, maybe I can turn this on. A lot of beeps. Something -- they are not a spoof movie of "the 2001" Odyssey." Let me proceed to the actual science. I want to discuss with you today. All right. Now, to go back to the title of this conference which says inspired by web emerging results. The question, did the web already -- and hopefully by the end of this talk, potentially as the web might have seen dark stars. I need to present the idea of the dark stars. I mentioned the work 20 times already. Let me tell you what they are. They are hypothetical as an object. Those guys could form whenever the first ones form in the conditions of -- the first stars -- in the simulation here on the left, you have molecular collapsing as the standard picture taken from Roman. the competition between gravity and heat eventually emerged with an object. The star, so on and so forth. In the picture, dark matter is not included. An object that will eventually sign because of nuclear fusion. The question that was posed in 2007 was, could this standard picture be modified throughout of this collapse of a molecular cloud picture. The answer they found is yes, indeed. This picture could be modified. I need to learn left versus right first of all. They found that three conditions upon which you know longer -- the collapse of this molecular cloud is stopped when the of magnitude intensity before any reactions can take place. Sufficiently high -- micro hills do have -- second of all, you have to have cooling. Remember, those are pristine -- the worst you could ever have. Third of all, this is the particle physicist kind of insertion here. The dark matter and other products have to be trapped inside. Really found that typically work really well efficiently. Those subjects could actually form in the early universe. Now, let's build them up en masse a little if you will. To the supermassive dark stars which are the main object of my talk today. This is in the HR diagram. No need to explain it. Three different

masses. All those with the same annihilation -- you all know the standard cross-section. Some takeaways. The lighter -- and darker more efficient which is natural. They really can build up en masse. For solar masses. Potentially most of the variance surrounding them. The main reason for that if you look at this access and temperatures, cooler down to the fifth or ten to the fifth. Right? They don't need enough ionization radio nation. They call standard AC. Typically, dark matter -- meaning, they would include a lot of work. Close to the center. Now, another way to build the masses. I have -- [indistinct] Dark matter that is exhausted. You follow this pace of collapse. This object is contracting. The main leap of faith. The dark matter density -- you are going to end up with efficient capture. Which would again -- dark star face. Now powered by captured it dark matter. 2 distinct scenarios. Upon which we can build a supermassive star. Look at here. They can be as bright as into the nine or more. That is a single star. That is as bright as a galaxy. You know. And we can see them actually. So why do we care about it? Not because we can build them. It could actually solve long-standing puzzles and cosmologies such as this mystery. Where do those supermassive black holes many different quasars come from? People have nonstandard theories. They can either say, we accept -- which is fine. Or, they can say, we need the supermassive seed. Because they are not massive enough to generate those objects. Dark stars are the thing, then they could collapse and black holes, right? They would provide those subjects. Moreover, the Webb started to pick on the spot of what is happening in the early universe. To the point out, here I have the galaxies that were working -- not really about Stella. Let us fight -- okay. The galaxy -- but anyhow, those are problem that Webb guys were giving us or making a space. There's too many, too massive, too early galaxies are "galaxy candidates that are observed. That is the puzzle prayer that is really a puzzle. Namely if you assume that those are indeed galaxies, that means there are stars inside of them. Converted to stars above 100% efficiency. Which doesn't really happen in models. If you think about a dark star, those guys really can the variance surrounding them because they are cool very efficiently. Or over very quickly. I'm not can I go through the paper. It is a paper written by collaborator. Basically showed to say, okay, the problem in terms of early to massive objects. We tried to fix it with an extra -- cosmology. Can we do that or not? The answer is yes, you can. Intention. Right? Outside -- now quickly, observe are not dark stars. The main take away I want you to have from this talk is that we have candidates right now. Create such candidates. When collaborative work -- let me keep this slide details you can ask me at the end. Here, you all have probably seen this. The exposure, right? For that objects identifying back in '23, one of those is the most distant "galaxy" ever confirmed in the spectroscopy. We have spectra. This galaxy the redshift of 13, but now, we can fit this with a dark star. It fits very nicely. So that Jay-Z 12 -- Jay-Z 11. We didn't try that hard. Another words, it was rough. Basically, we found that generically, we can feed those where the metric data from the Webb with dark stars. Dark stars supermassive dark stars are generically a very good fits for the web data. Now there's more things to do. You see this thing here. It is a in them 1640 which is not present in early galaxies. They could potentially have a smoking gun signature. [indistinct] I don't want to eat into the nice conversation we are going to have later. I will just lead with this slide here. And I think the main take away. Right now, when I told you should no longer be viewed as sufficient as claiming this is a galaxy. I can probably -- dark star generic. So the main take away, we need high quality to be able to tell them apart. And with the Webb, what could Roman do with a wide field to test a lot of candidates. We good interplay that into the other instruments. Now we really need -- I'm going

to stop right here to give a chance for comment. Honestly to move on to greener pastures for the discussion.

All right, right there, the third row. Great talk. So, from the survey we have been finding candidates that are point sources. Some of them having redshifts that are high but not as high as 13. But they have red and blue. Is there any way to get that -- That question is really bugging us for a while. Okay. Where is the dust from? Maybe he could be one of those dark stars dominates in terms of converting to a black hole. And then you have some stellar. This is just stipulations right now. I didn't do the science yet. This is a great question. Thank you for asking it. We need to address it properly. We have one more as long as it is short. Well, I hope so. I just wonder if there are any other -- what is the signature of dark matter? What gives off energy obviously. Mostly very high energy. You know, dark matter still exist today. We should in theory see some advance of this if this is really happening. Another excellent question. There are some signatures. People claim that they censor -- there is some day. They actually feed it with a closer wing. The one thing we could do. We have never done it, but I think we should do it. Try to take those parameters that feed the galaxy and see what can we do with the distant stars. That is a good question. Thank you. I don't know if my answer was short enough. I will stock. We can talk more later. All right, perfect. That is the end of this talk. We will begin some discussion now. Thanks for all the speakers this morning. You all did fantastic. Loved all of them. You deserve a huge round of applause. Thank you.

The discussion will actually happen in the cafeteria. If you want them in person. We have six topics. Actually seven. Of the topics are on Slack. I will quickly read them just to make sure you can go. This is how those are pasted. On the cafe. Topic one, Roman community surveys are going to be defined by a community process. How do we as a community want to be able to engage with this process? What do we want to seek out in this process? So that is question number one. Question number two, what are your plans for dealing with the torrential data? Question number three, Roman data will be accessible to everyone with no preparatory period. How then would we approach grafting physics surveys that enhance the overall legacy value of the Roman data rather than addressing scientific inquiries. One of the most exciting prospects for Roman or exoplanets? For the Milky Way and nearby galaxies, 5. Galaxy evolution 6. Choose your own adventure, 7. So go out and mingle and pick a topic. The discussion session will happen again on Friday. Please select someone to synthesize your thoughts as that will be presented at the summary session on Friday. If possible, pick someone who will be here Friday. That's all. Please go on and chat.

Jinyi Yang: Probing the Early Universe using the most Distant Quasars

Welcome back, everyone. With the galaxies surveys and the higher universe. We will start with a talk from Jinyi Yang from the University of Arizona who's going to tell us about probing the early universe using distant quasars. On the early universe, the early universe with distant quasars. We have 27 minutes. Thank you. Can everyone hear me? Thank you so much for this opportunity. I introduced my recent work about using the most distant quasars to probably early universe. So talking about the quasars and show some preliminary -- observations of this

quasars. How we can use Roman studies for quasars. First, about quasars. Active nuclear scan of the galaxy. We can see the structure here in the center of each quasars, there is a supermassive black hole. We can see the outside region. And so, quasars have power -- they have high luminosity power supermassive black hole. Higher luminosity, we can go to distant early universe using quasars. From observations, they get observations of the power continuum and mission lights. Continual quasars spectral. And also we can see absorption features of this continuum emissions. From the spectral copy. And also the observation known as quasar have multi-emissions from x-ray to radio. Some have been observed. So, this -- if we go to higher shift. What we can learn using the quasars. The redshift about 6. 900 million years after the Big Bang. So we have learned these quasars provide us with valuable information on how this supermassive black hole at the early universe, early massive galaxies bring also evolution during the -- and also, the -- evolution at the early universe. And also, the environment early massive halos and structure surrounding quasars. All these science topics are why we want to learn. Why we want to study the redshift quasars. Some examples of how we can use this to study the early universe. The first one is during the Epoque. There is a typical quasars. Continual admission. If we go to high redshift, the line, blue part of the second fissure showing the quasars observed that neutral hydrogen in the high redshift. We can see quasars pillars -- this is a complete observable track. And also, in the forest, the videos from the neutral hydrogen in the absorption neutral hydrogen in the IDM. We call the video -- the features absorption features sewing quasars spectrum can be used as tracers of the IDM evolution hydrogen fraction. As a function of the redshift. Here is a figure show the quasars our estimate of the fraction from using quasars. High redshift quasars from redshift 52 redshift 7.5. Different measure for example. Effective -- pixels and also basics -- redshift about 6, we can see it. The increasing of the neutral hydrogen. It is very hard to provide -- on the inter-fraction. We only got the upper limit on the dark pixels. This work is highlighted by the group. We got this read out here. The only one from quasars at this redshift. At the high redshift we just gathered quasars estimates. We can see -- that is limited by the current spectral observation from ground-based telescopes and also for example, the modeling of the quasars. That is measured. This part actually -- we need to use -- the IDM evolution. Not to mention the quasars are central supermassive black hole in the quasars. We can learn about the supermassive black hole growth. And galaxy evolution. As an example here show the high redshift quasars redshift about 6.5 quasars. The redshift 6 quasars. In comparing with the low redshift populations black contours. As we can see, we have already know that this high redshift luminous quasars supermassive black hole close to the limit. And they have black hole massive -- so, this result actually is challenging the early supermassive black hole growth. We can see the black hole growth tracks from redshift 32 the redshift that we observed. Here that we require the very massive black hole. Our result is consistent with a more massive model. Cannot gather exactly inclusion. We need an example to measure the Black-owned mass more accurately. And also about black hole evolution. This is actually showing this figure. The possible evolution passes between the coevolution of the black hole in the galaxies from the early universe to what we can observe today. We can see different evolution -- so far observations of high redshift quasars and particularly, the luminous quasars. There could be supermassive black holes black holes compared to the host of galaxies. Relative to the relation we learn from local universe. That is the solid line. Here is the point from high redshift luminous quasars. The observations limited.

Our understanding about the quasars most of galaxies from similar observation. And mission from the also galaxy. Make and directly detect the stellar admission from the quasars host of galaxy correctly even with HST. We can see after the subtraction. The red panel here show us there is no detection outside of the central noise. It means that this limited our understanding of the coevolution between the supermassive black hole in the host of galaxy. That is also what we want to learn from space telescopes. And then, the over dense environment. This luminous quasars issued residing in over dense regions. Showing this figure that is a simulation. Surrounding us the central supermassive black hole, we see over dense environment. However, observations show inconclusive results as we can see in this figure. Surrounding the quasars in his field, we can see over dense region around this quasar. In this field and what we do now detect -- this also we went spectroscopy observation. We want to complete spectroscopic observations surrounding the high redshift quasar fields. Whether the quasars are in the over dense regions. The reasons why we want to learn high redshift quasars. And we can see here is the quasar number density from a low redshift to high redshift. About 5.5. Redshift decline toward high-rise shift. At the same time, we also have a contaminant that could be hundreds to thousands higher than the density. Within the gaps of our current surveys. 21 magnitude inch a band. So, I want to mention that is so far we have quasar sample at high redshift about 6. That is over the average from the high red shift quasar in the past 2 decades. Here is -- using optical and the data that is coverage of the surveys. Here is the recently our luminous quasars survey. Years ago, seem more and more quasars. We got a redshift of 6.5. From our luminous quasars survey. Now, we have -- relatively large high redshift quasars. After the launch of JWST, JWST opens a new era that we can observe a sample of high redshift quasars using JWST. And also JWST targeted quasars. JWST is targeting a large sample of redshift about 6 quasars covering a wide of the redshift and luminosity. So then next, show some preliminary regarding the study of the high redshift quasars from different aspects. The first part of that is the quasar optical admission in the supermassive black hole mass. Here is a template of the quasar spectral probe from telescope, until this region. The result -- the quasar Black-owned mass, for the Black-owned mass However, both of them are the most reliable tracer. We can now -- and in particular, submission line. This is to be the most reliable tracer. So that is what we want to use to estimate the black hole mass. This is early result from the aspire program introduced this program later with details. Rely here we can see diverse admission lines in particular for the oxygen line. Some of them with proud and blueshift. All three components. Some of them we know to attract a strong admission. And also some of them we have seen strong components. And that is the observation of the optical spectrum. The black hole mass. Compare the black hole mass with the black hole mass we have already opted. He was showing the results but at the conclusion is there are generally consistent. Which means, this observation can confirm the existence of the black hole redshift of 6.5. I'll also want want to mention there is a small train of the slightly smaller black hole mass. We are waiting for a large sample. And I also want to highlight this one. We got a few weeks ago. Amazing results for other redshift 7.5 quasar for the first one covering from the Reston optical port redshift redshift 7.1 quasar. This is a combination of the -- and also the data. We can also compare the spectrum with the ground pays for them measuring data metric data. And this one is from a program which called the quasar front tier program. We target quasar and redshift around 7.5 with multiple imaging. After we talk about the black hole, we moved to the host galaxy as we mentioned before previously with HST, we can

now detect the stellar admission from quasar host galaxy directly. If we get -- we can see here for the example from the aspire program. Original imaging that is quasar image. After the subtraction, we can get different tabs. Some of the galaxies claim no detection surrounding the quasars. That means it is weaker compacted host galaxy admission. Some of them Jose galaxy. It is the admission that looks dusty. And for some system, we confirm that they can be quasar companion systems with multiple companion systems here. This is what we can learn from the luminous quasar. There is a quasar sample targeting this sample redshift about 6. Here is the example. We can see also in the red, most of the galaxy. Detection of the quasar Jose galaxy, we can win sent to the black hole mass. As I mentioned before, observations are massive supermassive black hole. Looking at the near camp. There's no evolution from low redshift. From the quasars. Orange can curse the predictions based on the redshift 0 a relation which means assuming no redshift evolution. We can see that consistent with no evolution. So this result now tells us, it could be that this high redshift quasars is consistent with low redshift host relation. Again, we also need a later sample. And then, we can also look at black hole host using imaging. For example, here is the NIRCcam spectral. You just want to show before. That is broad. Blue shifted admission. This is the most extreme case we discovered. Extended from the last data. That is from the spectroscopy. I hope we can get the morphology and gas. Here are a few examples recently published this year. So we can see the redshift 6.8. The remission. Down here is to the redshift 7.5 quasars. We were here more details from the talk this afternoon. And also, I want to highlight this one. This is the companion system. We can see the admission. And the orange and red one from near spec. This year, a high quality spectral within this aperture so we can get the kinematics. We can get more details of the story of the system for that will tell us about the story of the example of the early quasars. Supermassive black hole and the host galaxies. So that is the posts. Environment also reviews some evidence about the over a denser region the early quasars. This is the JWST program. And target luminous quasar around 6. Here is one example. this is a quasar spectral. We have detected multiple fallacies. We can see here, this is about quasar redshift. Over a dance of the galaxies associated with the central quasars. There could be an over dense environment of the quasar. And also high redshift 6.5. As I mentioned before, this is actually a NIRCcam program for about 25 quasars. Redshift about 6.5. One program together with 100 -- program. Searching for the quasar environment. In the observations, the figure. This program has already come from confirmed more than 500 galaxies redshift. We also found that some of them are associated with quasars. This is one example in Winfield. We see the surrounding galaxies as they over denser region. Thank galaxies since that's, they are outlined with the structure. In more details about our program can be felt on that page here. So, as a brief summary, I mentioned about the preliminary results. So far, provides us the study with the existing quasars. Very deep and parallel studies of the existing quasars redshift of about 6. The result actually, our understanding from supermassive black hole host galaxy environment and evolution. However, I need to mention, JWST is not designed for wide-field survey of the new quasars. That is why we want to the next generation survey facilities for example, Roman. So with Roman, weekend probe of the distant quasars and -- the first one, the Roman steps figure here along with surveys of quasars redshift 9-10. That depends on the function. And so, about hundred quasars redshift 7. About the high latitude areas survey here. Redshift 7, 8, 9. We can see different numbers. Best on the current quasar function. This is what we expect about the new surveys. And here, for this, our group working on

the counter selections. A different redshift branch. We will hear more details this afternoon. And that is the quasar -- I also want to highlight some specific points. We can also have wide-field surveys of quasar. We are looking to the populations. Here is the point. Recently by JWST operation with a fraction Christian. There are some red dots revealed by the example here. We can see. The NIRCam can be well fitted with type one. Additionally, observations of high redshift galaxy revealed a component of admission line. This readout observation is a question about the higher fraction of redshift. So, regarding this part, we will have an answer from Roman with a complete wide-field spectroscopy yield of the quasar. Roman, we will highlight the Roman high spatial resolution and high sensitivity. To carry out systematic survey of the gravitational -- and particularly, the high redshift. Sorry. We know that so far there's only one quasars. No high redshift above 6. This one is actually discovered by the imaging data. As I can operation here, here is the image. We carry out the system. The system. Ground-based image. This is the image. We cannot resolve it. Roman spectral resolution will be comparable to HST. We can directly resolve it from the imaging data. We can carry out the systematic survey of them. And that as I mentioned, quasars surveys. An example of this high redshift quasars. We can study the evolution during the Epoque directly. That is the individual constraint best on individual above 7. We can see only a few here. For over existing quasars, we can get better constraints to redshift around 7 or 7.5. The next generation, a large example of the quasars. We can directly gather to trace of the evolution of the functional redshift from 6 to 8.5. Much better improved much improved here. So this is where we can learn for example Roman quasar sample. And also, the environment as I mentioned, we already got some evidence about the over dense region surrounding high redshift Illumina quasars. Relatively small. Relative to over dense region surrounding quasar. Over dense region. We can see this size is about 15 per minute here. Which means it is much larger than the NIRCam good with Roman, large scale over region with only 119. Over dense region. And that is a summary. We get more details. We can go deeper in the videos. Roman is good surveys above 6 quasars. Deeper field redshift later and diverse samples. And also, we already learned that Roman has high sensitivity, I resolution and we can also along in depth study of this interesting video. Still here and take questions. Thank you.

Thank you very much. Questions in the audience here or online as well. There is one question over there. Thank you for a very exciting talk. I was wondering, you mentioned that you have data as 158-micron line. You also have for what fraction of the sample. If you have this sort of this is coming, can you predict where those sources will go? You show that some of them are off the local. Where will they go? Thank you for the question. Actually for the high redshift quasars, few observations are relatively hard. We only have very few very limited example. With a mission observations. But I think we are building the sample. Typically after we gather the admission lines, it's relatively bright. We can learn more about it from the lines. Thank you. Any questions online? More questions from the audience. In the meantime, I have a little question. So at least from lower redshift that they are better probes of dense environments. Quasars or radio galaxies. I was wondering if you have any estimates on the power of your sources and if there is a correlation between that and the nearby environment. Good point and thank you. Yes, for the high redshift radial quasars, there observations. We are working on a program of high redshift radial basics to study the surrounding over dense regions that so far for this result, there

is no -- there is one observed. A few weeks ago. We haven't got that data. But for statistics, we need a larger sample. Thank you. Thanks for a great song. I was wondering about your black hole mass M_H beta. I think that -- they are kind of consistent within the contours but a lot of them seem to be above the relation. They seem to be smaller H beta masses. Are these sources -- do they have a certain ratio? Are they selected to be above or at a certain ways and how large of a sample are you expecting that you might populate and understand this relation a little better? Thank you for the question. Only the species from the luminous sample. An heirloom in a sample, they have a narrow ratio. We can see -- we can see they are consistent. We cannot get conclusions. After we finish the second one or data combined, we actually have 30 or 40 quasars that we can get a better statistic. There are -- we actually don't know whether it is correct or not so far. With 30 or 40, we will know that. We also can gather scattered compared to the low redshift. Thank you. We have time for one more quick question. There is nothing online. If not, let's think this speaker again.

Yuichi Harikane: A comprehensive JWST study on galaxies at $z \sim 9-16$ and its implications for the Roman surveys

So our next speaker we have Yuichi Harikane from University of Tokyo. Is going to tell us about galaxies and its implication. Yuichi: Hello I am from University of Tokyo. Today I will talk about in the z 9-16 galaxies. So this shows the history of universe. As you know in today's universe. In this context in the cosmic abrasion is important to understand the processes. In formation efficiency and multifunction and Aji in relation. And one of the most important is the formation as a function of the red shift and the rate so this black point shows and it shows and increases to zero. Several other studies can be explained by the model assuming the star formation so this redline in this model produce the evolution from 0-10. And also this model starts to predict a steep decline in JWST in the universe. So no JWST is finding many in ARO and ERS imaging cameras in 9-16. And the function of the red shift showing the JWST and select bear the black points show the H ST selected and you can easily understand the power of JWST in the high red shift in the universe. Showing the number so in JWST motivation with other HST motivations through 12, nine and 12. And then we compare with others so in the function again in the predictions. As you can see to under predict especially on the bright regime. May be more easy to understand just to show the number of 12 and the brightness of minus 20. So we have a total of four in very high. And the blue shows the number from the predictions and up to under predict such number. So JWST is now finding many surprisingly higher predictions. Using this indication here with the information in the function. The shows in the redshift in the observations. So for this, compare this JWST in in the redshift which shows in the introduction. To produce the revolution plan however this model starts to under predict. So building tension between the model predictions. So this may indicate a sum be different however there is one caveat. All of these have the data points based over the redshift in the imaging. So there is always a constant about the redshift. in the wretched 16 the spectrum to be 4.9 is a very strong emission lines and imaging. So we definitely need data to discuss whether the star formation is higher not. So that's why we are now investigating this data set. Over 25 directions and an 8.5 in the redshift. This includes in 0.04 and the brake and the omission line. In the data sent to me in the images indicated the lower image shows higher rate and predictions. So from the spectroscopy we find

the indication between the JWST motivation and predictions. In a shift of less than ten. And the efficiency the star formation is higher than 5% in comparison to the universe. The other possibility is many AGN populations in the observations are finding many whose numbers or productions are higher redshift and these are also many populations made in the universe. For the possibility in the function and the possibility in high redshift in the temperature is high, IMF and CMB so for particular even 10% because the temperature is high in the function. So it shows that KV in the rate the background is our assumption. Factor is similar to this, however it is heavy in the function because the top ABI makes many stars that contribute in the galaxies. So can also explain. So we are now finding many in our predictions and three possibilities. So we are finding many galaxies however in the brightness only a few, very small number. This is because HST and JWST have a very small area in view of HST and JWST. However it is very interesting for example into the temple of 6, this is very bright showing this. And interestingly the emission lines are very strong. This indicates super solar ratio. It cannot be easily explained as it is by models. And some studies report so the galaxy is very interesting and these things that Roman can find hundred thousand in galaxies by including long wavelengths between Roman and we can nicely investigate very bright galaxies on JWST. So this is the last before my summary so you can go over the redshift and see investigating galaxy revolution. And imaging on the spectroscopic instrument and the instrument of Roman in the motivation is very important. So this is the summary of my talk. The modern production can be flamed by high SF efficiency in the function and Roman from 100 to 1,000 bright galaxies at ten. Thank you.

Thank you very much, now questions or you have 3 minutes. You can ask a question. Very interesting talk thank you so much. I have a question about the top-heavy IMF results, I'm sorry if I missed it, but what type of talk of the IMF? In saltpeter what is the exponent you have to assume to make or model? I didn't explain in detail. So here you can see 2,000 models 1500 or 50 solar mass to 500 solar mass. This is kind of assuming a different shape or different slope. Image making the low factor. Any more questions? Online? So I was wondering for the redshift above 12, so I mean those are rare in galaxies, right? I was wondering if you have evidence to be associated with cities that would boost of the density that you measure? That's a very good point. It's possible with the bright galaxies they can be over in all of this in cosmic variances in variance affect in model predictions. More questions? Thank you, Yuichi, again.

Minghao Yue: Gravitationally lensed quasars in the reionization era, the prospective for the Roman Telescope

Next speaker we have a Minghao Yue who will tell us about quasars In re ionization. Can you hear me? Yes so I am Minghao Yue I am postdoc at the Institute so first of all let me say a big thank you to the conference organizers and all of my amazing collaborators. Today I am very happy to get this chance to talk about high-redshift gravitationally lensed quasars and how it's a game changing this field. Now lensed quasar a very valuable useful objects in astronomy enabling many studies for example if you're using lensed quasars especially the Hubble constant, and we can also use them to probe the structures of the foreground lensing galaxy especially if they are mass for files and their CGM structures. And also with the help of lensing we can get a magnified view of the supermassive black holes meaning we can probe the faint

Quasar population as a small-scale structure in these galaxies. I would say in principle, you can carry out these studies for lens quasars in all but in this talk I will specifically focus on high resolution because I think if you are primarily interested in cosmology if we have some high resolution lens quasars, and five or sixish, that will give us a better constraint on these prompters. If we are interested in the Russian Revolution of the galaxy structure, and now we do want to find some more that are likely lensed by galaxies. And to me I think the most important point here is in lensing magnification is more useful for high vision objects because higher resolution are fainter so there are some studies we cannot do with nonlensed objects that we can do or it can only with lensed objects. Just as an example here I am showing at 6.5 those mentioned over 39 we discovered these lensed quasars a couple of years ago and ever since in the follow-ups of the systems and as I mentioned there are some that are not available that we do detect for this Quasar. For example the CO lines we just mentioned, I mean usually it's not available before this, lens Quasar we see the entire CO letter for this week it is a very detailed analysis. I am not going to go into details of these studies but we can do many important studies that are otherwise inaccessible. I should probably mention that this Quasar is a target of JWST GTO observations and I'm very looking forward to the results. That is why we want to find more dense quasar but unfortunately this one is still the only one we have confirmed. In quasars they are more than 700 known quasars. But none is only when we have confirmed that his lensed. A lensed fraction of about 1% there is some theoretical studies trying to predict the lengths fraction of high-resolution quasars which results range from 0.5% have been 10% which is a wide range about because fraction depends on the function you assume in the full-blown galaxy population and also serve a depths, et cetera, but my point is even the most conservative case, this comparison still suggests that we might be missing a large fraction of lensed quasars at higher shifts. If you wonder why this is the case, we can have a look at some simulated images of high resolution lensed quasars and by looking at these images, my feeling is that first of all many of them are kind of blended. Meeting these are simulated which tells me usually ground-based spatial resolution is not going to be sufficient to solve the lensing structure making it very difficult for us to identify these objects. And also, the full-blown galaxy in these systems are pretty bright compared to the Quasar which means traditional service heavily rely on their colors to identify promising candidates. But with the contamination of the galaxies, the color section will fail so that's another reason why we failed to see some of these quasars. These points in mind I will notice that Roman would be a very ideal facility to service for a lensed quasars only because it is a very sharp ASF allowing us to fully dissolve the structure but in imaging, it will also have spectroscopy hey. So you don't have to bother color selection we can see the full-blown galaxy and confirmed the Quasar. As it was in mentioned that Roman has a pretty large survey area allowing us to build a good sample of these objects. And motivated by this consideration I ask myself how many lensed quasars at higher shifts are we going to be able to detect with Roman? And how should we find these objects? All right, in honor to predict or to estimate the statistics of lensed quasars, apparently we need to have some information about the foreground galaxy and the background Quasar population and with this information we can do some simple math to get the statistics of lensed quasars. By statistics I may not only the number of lensed quasars we can detect but also something like the distribution of lensing separation and the distributing of full-blown galaxies, Russia, et cetera. And so I decide to write a simple piece of code and it works out pretty well. I can get all the statistics with one minute

oratorical and I validated this code against some catalogs to make sure it works. Here I am going to consider two populations of objects, the first one that is luminous quasars which we all know and the other is a newly discovered population the faint which are newly discovered from recent JWST observations if you are not familiar this is what they look like and you can see in near cam images these appear to be point like sources with pretty red colors and they have broad emission lines that indicate they are active with material in their center. Now I can predict the statistics of lensed quasars and Rome on I see a few upcoming surveys and now we can have a look at the results. So first, let's consider luminous quasars. I calculate the number of lensed Quasar we can detect in the survey and this number is number is -- read should be on the 6. About 10. About 3 in Roman. Doesn't have sufficient survey area compared to the other 2. If we look, I think this is exactly where Roman shows his power. First of all, we are still going to find many of them. As I am showing here, most of those are concentrated below 7. If we want to probe, we do want the power of Roman. In this case, it's probably too shallow to study these objects. I think these numbers are pretty exciting to me. Before I go any further, these results with caution. Because the loss of functionalities are highly uncertain. Looking at these numbers, easily ten times larger or ten times lower. That is why we need Roman. We want to figure out how many objects are there in the universe. I hope I have convinced you that Roman has a great potential to find these quasars and Ag ins. I want to spend a few more words about the unique advantage. Let's go back to this luminosity function again. If I mark the survey depth on this figure four -- this is what they look like. This is without a lens magnification. If I add some typical lens magnification, this is what they look like. Go back and forth to just have another look. My favorite thing about these figures if we want to study the tale of those AG ins, we really need a combination. For other surveys or for Roman without lensing is pretty hard to reach this part. That is I think the unique advantage of Roman. And also don't forget Roman has very unique advantages. I'm running out of time. One last thing is we are trying to get prepared for the upcoming surveys by making use of current data sets to find more lens quasars. We are making progress. I'm going to put my summary here. I'm happy to take any questions. Thank you.

Questions. While everyone is thinking about questions, I was wondering if you actually find it less quasars and what you expect with Roman and if you can derive anything about the structure of formation, any constraints. I mean, anything we can find with Roman, we find more or less then we expect. It will be very interesting. That means if I go back to this illustration, it means something is wrong with either our knowledge about the foreign galaxies or quasars. If we do find fewer -- first of all, if we have a good knowledge about the quasar function, I assume that. If that is the case, we probably -- that means we probably are missing some galaxy populations. There's fewer galaxies than we previously saw or they are less massive or it can happen in the other way. If we find more than we expect, that means there are hidden population of full grown galaxies. That will be a very useful indicator of galaxy evolution. Thank you for the interesting talk. Roman can detect many -- do you have any idea about the spectroscopic -- is it enough? Yeah, I think -- well, I have listed some here. These are all for imaging. Obviously, the spectroscopic will be more shallow than this. My personal suggestion would be for the brighter and back of the AGNs and luminous quasars. We can use the quasars and prism to do the job. We can primarily rely on the imaging to do a good candidate selection

and then we go to JWST. That would be my personal recommendation. Questions here online. If not -- Thank you very much. Okay, Jaime.

Wei Leong Tee: Predicting the Yields of $z > 6.5$ Quasar Surveys in the era of Roman and Rubin

The next speaker, we have Wei who's going to tell us about high redshift quasars and Rubin. About 10 minutes. I hope everyone can hear me clearly, right? Good. So first of all, I would like to thank the organizers for giving me this opportunity to talk about my work on this Roman approach for the quasar frontier where people in front of me already introduced a lot to you about what quasars are. Here I am trying to push the quasar frontier meeting going to the further -- we can reach. I am a graduate from the University of Arizona. Here I list the collaborators for this work and also your distinguished focus on the study of the earliest supermassive black hole in the universe. Why do we care about the high redshift quasars? On the bottom left, I show you some of the direct theories trying to explain the growth of the supermassive black holes in the universe. Since the discovery of 6-7 quasar, over a massive black holes has been raising issues on how the universe can grow such a black hole in such a short time. Popular theories trying to address these questions by coming up with some real different black hole scenarios to explain that. On the right, from -- this is an extrapolation of the black hole growth. Supermassive black holes back to where believe the first. It seems to have some favorites on popular theories about it cannot continue with the other possibility yet. All of the quasars that we recently discovered, they are all luminous, bright quasars. So they are missing a bunch of populations a little bit less massive than the over massive black holes which we read to, refer to. My work within from the focus on this. But first, I want to understand how it grows to such face in their redshift. My bottom line, and I show you a number that is the profile as a function of redshift of quasars. This redshift quasars has been coming less and less. Collective evidence of these quasars being less and less in higher redshift in the universe. The measurement has been up to redshift 7. Observations. The first question, and we find any quasars in redshift above 8. How do we find it? They are already predictions work on trying to search for the luminous bright quasars at redshift 8. There is also a recently paper on finding redshift 8.6 AG in far less. To be impossible quasar that we can find at redshift 8. Then how do we deal with -- are there any missing quasar that we haven't found? They are more abundant than most of the case. Can we find them? Ongoing project from the strategy program is trying to look for the quasars. My interest is trying to seek an Roman can help to target these two questions on finding that most highest redshift quasars and also finding many that can help us constrain the populations. Traditionally, the classic map that we can find quasars is finding true methods. These higher redshift quasars are primarily not detections in the blue events. I show you one of the quasar front deer 7.6. V5 is not detected in the optical image. The methods and below, I show you the spectrums. To actually find the high redshift quasars, we deftly need a deep enough wide payments that aced can help us in opticals and also to actually detect them. Okay. The surveys that we keep in mind is first we need deep optical. The legacy surveys are going to map 20,000 square degrees. Reach around 26. It is really deep enough. We can see the Roman space -- which we provide good enough. A prompt down to 26. To actually discover him for that target. The previous survey. But even with the Romans and Rubin's activities, we

are limited. We have been optimistically talking about switching for quasars. Practically, we need to confirm this. Contamination comes into play when you try to do -- show you one of the quasar simulations and also some of the contaminants. In our quasar surveys which is -- if we simply using the method to send the quasar candidates, all of the quasars will be singular it methods of the prominent colors and all those rising up. They will be easily picked up by this drop box methods. On the right, I will show you what other related of these populations. So, the blue and the green are the low redshift galaxies. The greens -- I read is the quasars. As you can see, both galaxies are like standard equations. Even if you can actually select any contaminants into your quasar candidates, the spectroscopic -- you just cannot rule out them completely before you are doing -- and it will take you a lot of time to come from them which is very impractical. Our experiment from the past is 6.5 spectroscopic 30%. You obviously can catch quasar candidates. It's worse and worse when you go to higher redshift. They become a lot worse. We definitely need to improve the understanding of the sources. Trying to improve our selection methods using these Roman/Rubin strategies. Available to us to improve our success rate in this case. Our strategy is we simulate all the species galaxies with some models with flux, colors, densities and observations. I don't have time to talk much detail about it. Come to me if you need more details. Our selections methods and how the completeness behave as functions of magnitude spirit here on the right, I show you the model. That we created. There are two things I would like to get your attention on. The functions, and one scenario, the favor of the model prayer the other one is quasar models. In our studies, the last model because more loud in the quasars and their measures. And also for the galaxies part, simulations because they do not estimate the galaxy's contributions in magnitude and initiated regions where it is primarily our interest region of finding quasars. So here, show you a quick plot of what the results can be. The black box marks the region that we are interested. Here I show you an example of the selections. Trying to select quasars where you can see that quasars you are looking for. So, we use a primarily colored -- to select quasars. We find that we get a very good clean result. That is good. We found the contamination itself is a strong function of magnitude. To further reduce the contaminants, we decided to join another selection which is a model comparison which includes the surface densities of the target population and the trial. And calculate the probabilities. Good understanding of the target population models where you know exactly where they are. The model colors and flux. This model method has detected the first redshift quasars. So we decided to do a joint selection of this where we apply. It's fast and effective to select a bunch of quasar candidates. We joined a basic method to reduce more contaminants. So for our results, on the right, I show you the overall efficiency as a function of magnitude. Our overall completeness in selecting the high redshift quasar is almost 90%. Rhys Ealy provides a very clean sample, elect current of quasars and also the selections dropped to 20%. It is still good deeper than current surveys. The main contaminants. If you go further, the contamination is much higher. And JWST can detect redshift 9 quasars. We try to see if proper motions can help. With a high latitude areas survey with a maximum separation of 4 years, we can maximize the motion to detect. We can reach -- so, this will detect 200 quasars at redshift 6.5. Looking for species to provide the constraint on quasars slope where we can determine the number on the right, I show you what is the best difference between 2 different populations of function model predictions. So what will be the JWST role? As we said, we want the community survey as a survey machine. Good redshift machines. And they are already some studies on trying to get

this low quasar properties and papers discussing that. The Wei Leong Tee feedback on this quasars, we can see more detail about that. Simply put my summary here. Any questions. Thank you for listening today.

Thank you very much. Questions in the audience from online. Everyone is thinking. Did you think about synergies with radio surveys and selection of function for quasars? That you care about radio and all? Currently not yet. There will be an interesting point. Because radio can give another aspect of finding the quasars.

Weizhe Liu: Probing the host galaxies of first quasars at $z \sim 7.5$ with JWST data

Next up, we have Weizhe Liu who is going to tell us about the host galaxies of high redshift quasars. Can everyone hear me? My name is Weizhe Liu. Thanks the organizers were giving this chance to talk about our recent work on ways our host. I'm currently working on the group and the EREBUS team. Studying quasar host galaxies from across time. Today, I'm going to talk about unveiling the quasar host galaxies that caused McDonald with high field observations. . So it's not working. Okay, we talked about a lot. We now know that there are numerous quasars and supermassive black holes exist within the first billion years of the universe. We still don't understand how the supermassive black holes in their host galaxies are coming into being within such a short period of time. That is my motivation of my research. And in the local universe, there is a tight correlation between the mass of a supermassive black hole in the host galaxy mass. This kind of suggests that the host and the galaxy host make charter across cosmic time. However, we don't know how that happens. We look at the earliest quasars at Charles McDonough when both of the black holes and galaxies are starting to form. We can understand how they interact with each other. We know a few things. Here are two examples. On the left, this color on the points are the location of the quasars and this black hole mass. Early quasars. Host galaxy compared to the massive black holes. It is likely that we are seeing in early -- compared to most galaxy. However, it is likely that we are -- the most massive ones that are most luminous in the universe and some selection in effect to it. In addition on the right side, we are looking at the rate of the host galaxies as a function of the quasar luminosity. The rate of this most galaxy at because McDonald can range from several tens to several thousand solar mass per year. Which means they are forming stars very rapidly. Taking this altogether to argue that the host galaxies may be the best place to witness the growth of first generation of massive galaxies and how they interact with supermassive black holes. Before this, most of the results we are seeing. Focused on the cool grass in this galaxies. They are still missing the component from the host galaxy which can be probed by Webb. Around this very deep -- two of the redshift list 7.5 or so quasars from the redshift range of program 64 which I've already been mentioned in the talk earlier. And basically, very deep for data. As I show here. You get a data cube which is three dimensions. 2 and the spatial dimension and one special dimension. For each spatial location within the source, you can get a spectrum. And so, our observation have a special solution. And, it has probed very suitable to probe the seller confident in the host galaxy of quasars. But before we see the host galaxy, there is only one challenge. That is the quasar is so bright. A quasar is a point source. This is an image of one of the redshift 7.5 quasar from the program stacked along the wavelength range. It looks like very similar to. PSF. To really try the

quasar and see the host galaxy. This is how we do it. I'm talking about a technique used called the effect. The idea is kind of straightforward. We have this. For each spectrum from this special pixel spectral is made up of three components. The quasar admission from the PSF, the host galaxy and the admission line from the host galaxy. What should we do. First of all, we can build a special template from the innermost region where the pure quasar admission. For each spectral, we can fit it with three components. Quasar template with a factor -- and some polynomials representing the host galaxy admission. Finally, a set of functions representing the emission lines from host galaxies. We finally -- see the host galaxy. And that his preliminary results we see in one of our sources. It is a ratio of 7.5. Hear what we are looking at the host galaxy. Admission line and the optical after the quasar has subtracted from left to right. We are looking at the flux. And of the central velocity of this emission. As indicated by this Red Cross. Looking at this map, we notice that this emission is extended on scale. I have said from the quasar center. It's quite large. Dispersion of 400 per second. Highly blue shifted. Down to minus 1. So it is likely that we are seeing driven by the quasar in this galaxy. If that is true, we can compare the properties to other in the universe. Here we are looking at the velocity as of function in the left. And the rate as a function on the right. Our object, the two triangles are some recent discovery of redshift 6.8 quasar which also have -- other from -- easily tell that these objects in the other driven redshifts. This condo supports the ideas that the broader mission we see really come from past quasar driven outflow in the sewers. This implies that quasar feedback from the outflow may already take place in the earliest iteration of quasars. And, we can see from our data, that galaxy is likely compact. Here, it means the off side of outflow of our source. This downward triangle indicates the upper limits of our source. Which we have not detected any extended yet. It is the upper limit. In comparison, the points are starting before. The black line is a resolution of the size of the forming galaxies from the study. We can see that the size of our object is likely compact and similar to those forming galaxies or AGN in similar redshift. Finally, I just want to -- to better understand the quasar host galaxies in this arrow. We really need a larger sample, a more diverse sample of quasars at a higher redshift for that is where Roman can help a lot. We already heard about from the talk, Roman can definitely help find more quasars in the early universe and can help us further study. And that is my talk. I will stop here and happy to take any questions you have. Thanks. Thank you very much. Thank you for the exciting results. I see that in the beginning of the talk you mention this similar relation in the star formation rate. Generally higher redshift quasars. You have three lines. Is there any way to measure the velocity dispersion or star formation rate using this line and compare it to observations if there are any? That is a nice question. This one is one quasar. It's not really possible. More likely due to the outflow. It's not very motion at all. I would not trust any dynamical mass from the emission. Hopefully we can have more data on this and velocity field are more regular velocity. Then we can have a better environment and compare them to the ratio sources. That is a very nice point, thanks. Have you compared the features of outflows using other -- have you first detected narrow components for the H beta? Not yet. For now, the only prominence -- most promising -- we don't have a clear detection yet. Very broad day. And of difficult to distinguish from the host galaxy or from the quasar itself. It is the forbidden line. It is much easier. It cannot come from the borderline region. To be seeing in our data. Detection and put a nice upper limit on it. We know there are some anomaly for the -- probably, the coverage for this. Can you trace the HR flow? So, I think we will be working on the data to see the results.

Integrated special. We have time for one last question. Let's think this speaker again. Thank you.

Micaela Bagley: Surveys of Galaxies at High Redshift with JWST and Roman

I believe the next is online. Can you share your screen? We don't hear you. Micaela, we're showing you as unmuted. Sorry about that. Well, thank you. Sorry again for all the technical problems here. I really want to thank the organizers for this invitation and also for their flexibility and presenting remotely and extreme patience with me as I respond to everything quite slowly trying to learn how to read function with a very young infant. Anyway, thank you all for your patience with these technological problems. I am Micaela Bagley, I am a postdoc working with Steve. Today, I will be presenting some results from the CEERS and surveys with JWST and also some results and worked on as part of the cosmic that by -- taking a step back and looking at some really broad questions. I'm really interested right now and looking and addressing when the first galaxies formed in the universe, how quickly did they build up their mass? What was the Galactic contribution to the reauthorization. Answering these questions are addressing these questions really requires that we understand the population of galaxies both faint and bright understanding how stellar feedback affects the faint end. How feedback affects the bright end of luminosity function. Star formation efficiencies play a role. It really requires that we sample the full population of galaxies. As we heard from the excellent talk, this is strongly connected to the cosmic star formation rate density. Very preJWST results. This is a plot showing the cosmic star density. What is important to note here is up to redshift 8, observations generally agreed. Towards higher redshifts, observations started to -- this is all preJWST. Observations started to disagree. Some observations were favoring a more smoothly declining density. Some were favoring a more rapid decline. As we have seen from results today and in recent papers, this dichotomy is being pushed out to even higher redshift with JWST. The real question here is, you know, how can we explain the density of galaxies that we are seeing in the early universe based on their star formation efficiencies? And so, looking at the density of galaxies that we are measuring. I am showing here, 2 luminosity functions in the upper right is focusing sort of on the bright end of the luminosity function using shallow HST parallel observations. And then focusing more on the more faint end in the lower left luminosity function in 2015. I was showing there are many great studies to look at. When I'm trying to highlight is that the densities that we are measuring where a little bit all over the map. In some cases, this was results varying by a survey strategy. In some cases like in the lower luminosity functions here, what we are looking at is a real variation pointing to pointing. We are looking at variations in the field to field variations. Our results as we pushed two major magnitudes are being affected by cosmic variance. This becomes really important if we want to understand what the Galactic contribution. Integrating down the UB luminosity function to some low magnitude limit to determine the density of nonionizing photons. Under some assumptions of models on ionizing efficiencies and escape fractions, we can start to understand what the available ionizing version. This is all depends on us getting a really robust measure of -- so I am going to -- to talk about the cosmic evolution early release survey. It was an ERS program or is an ERS program that was designed to get extra electric gate at to the community right away. This thing here, the P.I.s, it is really a team of over 150 scientists. This image is from our recent collaboration meeting this past month.

CEERS to briefly describe what the survey is. CEERS has this -- we are observing in the EGS field, observations came in a couple of Epochs. Some in December and some in June. If you and February of 2023. We have ten plus points depending on how you can with a variety of different prime parallel combinations. This figure shows just sort of, like, that super chaos that became the final survey. I think this version is called, like, version final underscore 2, really final. But I will break it down a little bit here just to show what we are working with. We have ten Rubin near imaging 20. On the left spread wide field data. We have eight mirror imaging findings and we have 6 near spec pointing's even though there are eight in that figure. We had data taken in a couple of epochs. We are still counting them at six pointing's. I just want to highlight the folks who are really working in the trenches trying to get these data projects reduced on the -- I am working on NIRC2 imaging. Working on our data and works on our near spec. Quick plug for CEERS. If you're interested in anything our science, our papers, check out our website. You can find us on Twitter if you are still there. You can access our data on our website. And we have a paper out describing our NIRC2 data reduction in our reduction scripts. Check that out. Why CEERS? Just like there's a lot of disagreement in the observations, there were a lot of sort of variety -- there was a variety of predictions pre-JWST of what we would see from models. CEERS is sort of optimally designed to constrain the models predicting galaxies, galaxy density in the early universe. The real question when we first got our data is will be to take high redshift galaxies. Greater than 10 or so. This image that I'm showing is our mosaic for the first four pointing's we got in June. Really right away, almost a 1, we found a high redshift galaxy. Redshift 11. It is named Macy's galaxy after the daughter. We start up selected it on her birthday. It is a surprisingly bright galaxy candidate that was really not predicted by simulations. What I am showing on the right here is a figure showing the predicted number of galaxies greater than redshift 12 and brighter than the brightness of Macy's galaxy from a variety of simulations. These include hydro, semi analytic models and semiempirical. Really, none of them would have predicted that we found this galaxy. The silk model gets -- if you remove all the attenuation which is what that shows, you would start to see this. Really this was unexpected. Starting to indicate really only results that we are seeing a lot of extra star formation. Redshift a 10. So using the first four pointing's, we got our first set of high redshift galaxy candidates showing their magnitude and photo metric redshift distributions here and Macy's galaxy is the one with a star. We were able to get our first luminosity function. The CEERS measurements here are shown in red. Other surveys were shown in orange. HST and ground-based studies are shown in light blue. The blue curves are showing an evolving double power level of function that is fit to data from redshift's 4-8. It extends that speculation down to redshift's 9-12. What we see here is that CEERS data points even though in the inset graph, we can see they are peeking around redshift 11. The CEERS data points exist at the upper envelope of what is expected from redshifts 9-12. This evolution in the luminosity function slowing down as we get to these redshifts. In December, we got the rest of our six points. Showing a full CEERS, salmon-colored. Naturally, what we want to do with that but look for more high redshift galaxies. We are showing here is our sort of complete redshift greater than 9 galaxy sample or a sample of galaxy candidates brothers 89 of them. And I will come back to talk about this in a minute for the squares' figures show those that have been spectroscopic Lee confirmed. However, CEERS by itself as a fairly narrow dynamic range in magnitude. We want to combine it with the next generation extragalactic exploratory public survey. This is a program that is P.I.d. It comes in 2

parts. One is an ultra-deep spectroscopic survey. That is working with the reduction calibration of that data set. The other part is an ultra-deep NIRCcam imaging survey on the UDF parallel field. This is the deepest imaging in the sky and perfectly aligns with that. This data set is being worked. The net effort. The main science goals are to constrain the feedback mechanisms of mass galaxies across cosmic time. On the nearest side, we are looking at measuring the slope and the scatter of the end of the mass relation. That low redshift. On the NIRCcam side, looking at measuring the slope of the faint end of the luminosity function. It also has been observed in 2 epochs. We are able to add 1.5 magnitudes of dynamic range to the luminosity function. This is a figure from the paper that came out early last week. Showing the luminosity function including red circles there. When we combine it fully with CEERS, we see that it really does agree with the slowing evolution of the UB luminosity function. Another way to look at this is in the surface density of galaxies. Showing the cumulative surface density as a function of redshift using the CEERS data. Again, we have seen this in the top where we have seen this and a lot of clocks today and other JWST papers. The JWST results at high redshift are higher than can be predicted by existing models of galaxy evolution. How can we explain this? One clear thought would be low redshift interlopers. Our samples very highly contaminated. We will jump right in that and say we don't think so. But certainly, we need a lot more to follow up to confirm. These are figures from several CEERS near spec follow-up of candidates in the EGS field. Confirming them between redshifts of 8 and 9 or so. Adriana, 9, and 10. Including Macy's galaxy in the upper right. We can sort of tentatively, you know, tentatively conclude that it is not entirely low redshift causing this. We heard from a great example of how we are seeing a lot of low luminosity AGN in galaxies samples at high redshift. There's is showing an example from a couple of papers. Rebecca Larson seeing some broad components spectroscopic components and our fellow upper these are sodas that have photometric CDs that are dominated by stars. They have spectroscopic signatures of AGN. As we have heard today, we are seeing plenty of these low luminosity AGN become a very red sources. They need to be fed by multiple components that and so there is a lot of exciting work to be done here to really start to quantify the AGN population. We have also heard that more efficient star formation good have a huge role to play here. I am leaving these as an open question that we want to explore. Cycle 2, cycle 3, and of course with Roman. How will Roman help? From now on, I'm going to sort of finish by talking about work that we did as part of the cosmic God. This is led by James. The question was, you know, where is Roman's place given all the results that JWST is providing? I am bringing back the CEERS luminosity function to show the purple box now is highlighting this sort of space that the high latitude wide area survey will be able to probe. Sort of assuming a magnitude limit of 26.9 in the redshift of 10.5. We are saying that it is going to be credible at really nailing down the bright end of the luminosity function. So important. These galaxies are very rare. They require large areas to sample the full population. You'll notice that the rest of the luminosity function is untouched. What we need is a deeper survey to help constrain both the need in the faint end of the luminosity function especially as we push to high redshift. and understand the ionizing photon budget. So this motivated a project to really look at. What could we get from a Roman deep field? We went about this using the Santa Cruz semi analytic model for galaxy formation. And, I'm going to sort of skim through some of these summaries about what it gives us and really point you to Aaron Young's recent paper from 2023 on describing the light cone and providing multiple iterations of it and also see his talk on Thursday for the next

generation better and better that he keeps creating. The sand that we are using for this survey is based on the multi-dark suite of dark matter halos and from that, constructed a 2 degrees square light cone that goes out to redshift 10. It is used to use predicted physical properties, about four at 12 all Roman filters. Andy provides a catalog of mock photometry that has source positions that are fully motivated by the dark matter halos underneath. So, just to sort of visualize what we are talking about here. We all know that the Roman field of view is quite large and is going to help a lot in these types of surveys. I think it really helps to visualize it. When I'm showing here is a snapshot in between redshifts 6.5 to 7.5. Although they galaxies down to a limiting magnitude. 29.5. Are shown in black. And then, the positions of sources that would be observed if you look at this field with HST are shown in orange. With C 3. here in Orange. One very simplified Roman field of view. It has the same aspect ratio. What do we get when we measure? Zooming in, we can see that one of these HST plantings is in a region that is under tents and one is in a region that is Overton's. We see those results come out when we look at the UB luminosity function on the right. And he gives us true value of the light cone. 2 square degrees. The purple line of the squares are showing us what we would measure with Roman looking at this pointing. The orange, we can see from HST, one of the plantings would give us a density that was quite high and one that we give as a density that is quite low. The power of Rome and here really is marginalizing over all of the density variations. We are looking at what would it take to do a Roman deep field survey. Let's assume that we have 500 hours to play with. What is the optimal compromise for high redshift galaxy area depth and filter coverage. We have considered 16 surveys. We are covering 4 different areas which is approximately one Roman pointing. 4 pointing's and the full light cone which is 7 pointing spirit in each of those areas, we are looking at 4 filters sets. A base set which uses the R band filter. A set that as the F184 and a set that adds both. Here we can see, so we are seeing the area and magnitude sort of, you know. We are seeing a plot showing the area and magnitude that would be probed by these surveys in the context of other JWST surveys in black and HST surveys in orange. This Roman deep field but occupy a really unique space year of going deep but also going wide enough to start to probe some of these important results. I'm going to really briefly summarize some of our results here because we have a paper that will be coming out soon. I will defer most of our discussion to that. But we have done is for each of the 16 surveys, we photometric lay scattered that light cone. Then we sort of mock observed they galaxies. We photometric lay scattered them then read them through a full high redshift selection process using the full photometric redshifts and detections of significance is a different bands. We do a full completeness analysis purple contamination analysis. Here we are going to show a couple of the results. We do this for all 16 surveys. The goal is to find a sweet spot in these survey designs. Focusing first on the recovery, we know exactly what truth is. Looking at the different filter options. This figure is showing, for one Roman pointing what you would get for recovery as a function of F185 magnitude and redshift. We are seeing the filters sets. You may notice a few things. The recovery around redshifts six is really quite poor at all magnitudes in the left column. That is the column that does not use the R filter. It is not surprising that this does demonstrate that the R filter is needed. We can also see that the recovery is a bit low in the top row at the high redshift end and sort of towards different magnitudes. That is using the filter. Once you get up to redshift nine or 9.5, you really do need that 184 as an additional second detection filter. We can compare that with the contamination of galaxies in these samples. Because having high

completeness is great but not if you are swamped by contamination. We can see in the right column, you really are swamped by contamination at redshift 6 we don't know that filter. I will defer to the paper for our full results. This is demonstrating the play between the different pros and cons of each survey. So now, I want to show up any of our results from the luminosity function. This is showing luminosity function is measured in the single Roman pointing using all six filters at redshifts extreme and, 78 committed 9. decreasing in density and color. The thicker colored line in each redshift band shows the fit to the end scattered all light. This would be the true luminosity function with 100% completeness is 0% contamination. The thinner lines are showing them measured luminosity function that we get in 4 realizations that each cover .28 square degrees. They do generally recover the true value. There is still some scatter in there. Finding a way not just to minimize contamination and maximize recovery, really find a filter set in the area that allow us to fully constrain the luminosity function. And again, we are looking this box that I have been on here shows where the high latitude wide area surveys signal limit now plotted for the amount of redshift of nine Woodland. We do see that is really we just constrained -- it would really help nail down. It's going to be important to combine results. It still leaves us in need of a deeper option. We can take those luminosity functions and integrate them down to sub limit. I have chosen this 17 year and see what we get for the integrated nonionizing UV density. That is what is shown here. The solid black line is again the value measure from the fall the scattered light cone. The purple hashed regions shows what we are measuring from photometric lay scattered and observed. It selected through our high redshift selection process galaxies in a single Roman pointing. The plot is showing UB as a function of redshift where it is on a logarithmic scale. We have sort of put slices at each redshift bed to show you what that looks like on a linear scale. You can see that those values are scattered. They hug their true value. They bracket the true value quite well. One of the sort of questions here is that JWST is really good at going deep quickly and efficiently. Why do we need a Roman pointing? Why do we need a Roman deep field to constrain the luminosity function? Well, we can see if we look at -- if we look at what we would get sort of with synthetic JWST observations is that even, you know, CEERS and NGDEEP together are one realization. One observation of a single CEERS plus. We are stitching together that magnitude rages together to get the full dynamic range. It still sort of one pointing. And he would add a second pointing. It is a survey done in region are quite close. How swamped by cosmic areas with our results be if we relied just on the JWST deep field? We're seeing that we would be fairly swamped. We are seeing the same thing we saw before. About the origin is now showing what you would get for sort of the Hubble front field. This is combining eight different HST size surveys together and doing multiple realizations of that. The gray region shows you what you would get with multiple realizations of a CEERS plus a NGDEEP. It's important to point out that these Roman results are scattered. They have been photometric lay scattered every observed. These JWST results are not. They are completely on scattered. This is the best-case scenario for the results. And potentially the worst-case scenario for Roman. It is really excited to see how much better Roman does with this type of a deep field. So at that, a little bit of a whirlwind year. I will summarize briefly year. We and everyone is finding a very high abundance of break -- galaxies with JWST. This seems to be implying that they luminosity function is the evolution of it is slowing as we get to high redshift or there's a lot of really exciting reasons this could happen. We could be seeing increased star formation efficiency and seek their contributions. We could be seeing a changing of -- there's a ton of

possibilities to explore it a lot of really great questions to answer in the coming years. JWST is great for this. Really ideal for great studies. Ideal for follow-up for deep imaging follow-up. You really need -- a much wider area for deep coverage to really get down to the faint end of the luminosity function to overcome cosmic variance. Using the Santa Cruz -- we have started to do some mock observations to show how much improvement a Roman deep field would give us of this type of study. I will in the back there and take any questions. Thanks again.

Thank you very much. There is time for questions. There is one question. Thank you for the talk. I'm very impressed that -- I have very interested the potential contribution for the AGN prayer and I was wondering if you can say a little bit more about -- to estimate the contribution of luminosity. Particularly, collaboration on x-ray or something like this. Thank you. Yeah, that is a really great question. And a little bit outside of my expertise. I would love to do for that question to all of the wonderful talks we had this morning. The real experts on a GM. I can say that we have seen through the CEERS data, we are seeing these sources and NGDEEP. They are being found everywhere that we have had to really change how we fit SEDs and adding multiple components dusty star-forming galaxies and really combining a very, very blue component with a very red component to fit these data in ways that we haven't before. I think there are AG -- there are x-ray observations for a subset of the sample. I don't know the specifics. I don't know if that answers your question. Thanks. There is one question online. This is a question for me. The early JWST results, you are talking about a tiny fraction of the JWST data that will be available by the time Roman lodges. One account for the future incoming JWST data, Roman really teaches anything we don't already know about the luminosity function. 5-10 years from now. That is a really, really great question. I think my answer is just I'm so excited to see what both JWST and Roman get. I think we will see far more JWST deep surveys coming through in the next five years of course. Each one will still be limited to a relatively small area to go deep in that kind of time, you are looking at single pointing's. While they are very, very helpful and useful in getting that faint population, single pointing's are still going to be very effective by cosmic variance. I think you really well -- we will still need a Roman size deep field to maybe in five years, we find that we don't have to go quite as faint if we can combine it with all the JWST deep fields. We will still need some component that goes a lot deeper than the high latitude deep survey to really minimize the effects of cosmic variance. That is my opinion. Thanks. One more question here. If not, let's thank her again. Thank you, everybody. So this ends the session. Right now, and is a coffee break and then the workshop. The reception at 5:00 p.m. So let's thank all the speakers of this session again. Recording has stopped.

Live captioning was provided by CaptionMax. Some formatting and light editing was included by the Local Organizing Committee for added clarity, but there was no attempt to correct all live captioning errors.

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